

Isolation and molecular characterization of indigenous soil entomopathogenic fungi from agricultural and highland ecosystems of Pakistan for sustainable pest management

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Abstract

Entomopathogenic fungi are the most practical alternative for insect pests in livestock and agriculture. In Pakistan, fungal identification has primarily relied on morphological characteristics, resulting in a lack of molecular validation. This study aimed to isolate and molecularly identify indigenous entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) from different ecological zones in Pakistan to develop environmentally sustainable biocontrol agents. Three entomopathogenic fungi (EPFs), namely *Beauveria bassiana*, *Trichoderma longibrachiatum*, and *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, with their accession numbers PQ285129, PQ551091, and PQ415785, respectively, were recovered from soils in Balochistan, Punjab, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK). Morphological characterization was complemented by ITS-based molecular phylogenetics, confirming their species identity. These findings provide a basis for developing region-specific biopesticides for sustainable pest control. The successful isolation and confirmation of these fungal species from different provinces also highlights their natural adaptation to local environments. This baseline information addresses the existing gap in documenting native EPF diversity in Pakistan and provides foundational data for developing locally adapted, region-specific biocontrol formulations for future pest management strategies.

Keywords: Entomopathogenic fungus, Biological control, Isolation, Molecular identification, ITS amplification

Introduction

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPFs) have garnered significant attention in recent years as potential biocontrol agents for managing agricultural and veterinary pests, particularly in the context of sustainable agriculture and integrated pest management (IPM) systems to replace the use of chemical pesticides (Mantzoukas and Eliopoulos 2020; Muhammad et al. 2008). The use of numerous pesticides, including pyrethroids, organophosphates, organochlorines, and carbamates, is one of the traditional means of controlling pests. They also pose serious threats to human health and the environment. These threats result from their widespread distribution and have detrimental impacts on ecosystems and human health (Ahmad et al. 2024; Baz et al. 2021). Therefore, sustainable solutions that can mitigate these problems and successfully manage pest populations are desperately needed.

The primary reservoir for EPF is soil, and substantial populations of beneficial soil-borne organisms are indicative of healthy soils (Beemrote et al. 2024). Therefore, for biologically based pest management to be effective and dependable, it is imperative to investigate and utilize the potential of naturally occurring EPFs. Several factors significantly impact soil microbial communities, including geographic location, plant and soil types, human activity, and other biotic creatures (Dong et al. 2016; Orgiazzi et al. 2015).

Numerous studies have clearly shown how geographical and climatic circumstances affect the biodiversity and uneven localization of EPFs in soils. For instance, a study in Punjab revealed that forest soils had much more varied EPF than those in cultivated fields. In addition, it was shown that altitude, latitude, and habitat type had a strong impact on the region's EPF distribution, which was highly patchy (Wakil et al. 2013). Also, (Wakil et al. 2014) Conducted a survey of insect pests in stored grains throughout Punjab, and from the 25,720 insect bodies, they isolated 195 fungal strains. The four fungi *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, and *Lecanicillium attenuatum* were the most prominent entomopathogenic. Besides that, their research pointed out that elevation and latitude, among other location features, had a very significant impact on the occurrence of EPF, thus giving the main idea of the environmental factors' role in the distribution of fungi. A recent study (Qayyum et al. 2021a) focused on the examination of soils and insect cadavers from natural and cultivated areas in southern Punjab, and revealed that the diversity of EPF was favored by higher soil moisture and was adversely affected by higher pH, thus indicating that particular soil features have a significant impact on the presence

of fungi. However, there is still uncertainty about the precise species diversity and distribution of EPF in Pakistan, as these studies mostly relied on morphological identification with little to no molecular confirmation.

Native EPFs could potentially show increased virulence to local pest populations as a result of extended co-evolution and, therefore, be the most suitable candidates for biologically based control methods that are locally adapted (Ioriatti et al. 2022). It is said that the use of native strains will double the success of pest control in the area where it is aimed and additionally reduce the risk of the release of non-native species in the local environment (Javed et al. 2025).

Although Pakistan has multiple agro ecological zones, very few studies have examined the diversity, distribution, and biocontrol potential of the native EPF species, hence, there is a large gap in the development of regionally adapted, environmentally friendly pest management tools. Identifying unique EPF isolates from Pakistan is of paramount importance because of their potential for sustainable agriculture, local pest control effectiveness, farmer cost-effectiveness, research opportunities, and contributions to the understanding of biodiversity worldwide. This information is vital for developing innovative pest management solutions that increase agricultural productivity and sustainability (Usman et al. 2021).

Thus, the purpose of this study was to separate and identify EPFs from various ecological environments in Balochistan, Punjab, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This offers fundamental data necessary for the future development of locally tailored EPF-based biocontrol formulations by combining morphological and molecular techniques.

Materials and methods

Soil Sampling

A total of 270 soil samples were collected across the three provinces. Soil samples were collected following the methodology described by (Wakil et al. 2013; Wakil et al. 2014), with minor modifications to accommodate the specific requirements of the present study. In Punjab, a total of 100 samples were obtained from fertile agricultural lands, fruit orchards, vegetation-rich zones, and semi-hilly areas. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 100 samples were collected from hilly terrains, forested regions, and orchards to represent the ecological variability of the province. In Balochistan, 70 samples were gathered from upland valleys, forested patches, fruit orchards, and, reflecting the province's semi-arid to arid environmental conditions and distinct microhabitats (Table 1).

At each designated region, five sampling points were selected randomly, and soil was collected from a depth of 10 cm to obtain representative microhabitats. The five subsamples from each site were homogenised and combined to form a composite sample representing the overall site conditions. Each composite sample was standardised to a weight of 200 g for uniform processing and subsequently utilised for the isolation of entomopathogenic fungi.

Table 1. Distribution of Soil Samples Collected Across Provinces

Province	Sampling Sites / Habitat Types	Number of Samples
Punjab	Agricultural fields, fruit orchards, vegetation-rich areas, semi-hilly zones	100
Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Hilly areas, forested regions, orchards	100
Balochistan	Upland valleys, forested patches, fruit orchards areas	70
Total	—	270

(a)

Figure 1. (a), (b) and (c) Maps showing the three provinces of Pakistan, where sampling was conducted across different zones within each province.

Isolation of Entomopathogenic Fungi (EPF)

The soil samples were processed according to the methods of Bich et al. (2021) and Tuininga et al. (2014) with infinitesimal modifications, and three serial dilutions (10^{-1} to 10^{-3}) were made from each sample. The medium prepared for EPF isolation was potato dextrose agar (PDA) (Condalab, Madrid Lab). This medium was supplemented with 10 mg/l penicillin–streptomycin solution and 0.5 g/l chloramphenicol (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Each dilution (0.1 ml) was spread on

each plate. The plates were subsequently sealed with parafilm and placed in an incubator for 5-7 days at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a relative humidity 80% (RH) in the dark.

Sub-culturing and Purification of Entomopathogenic Fungi (EPF):

A diverse range of fungal colonies was obtained from the soil samples, encompassing both entomopathogenic and saprophytic fungi. To obtain pure cultures, colonies were subcultured on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates prepared as previously described. Each colony of interest was carefully transferred to fresh PDA plates to isolate individual fungal strains.

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) were initially distinguished based on their morphological characteristics and processed further for identification. Colony features, including shape, surface texture, margin, elevation, and pigmentation on both the upper and lower surfaces of the plates, were recorded following established protocols (Arifah et al. 2023; Hatting et al. 1999). Subsequent microscopic examination of EPF genera was performed according to Humber (2012), focusing on the arrangement and structure of hyphae, conidiophores, and conidia. Plates were stored at 4°C until further use. Within each site, the morphology of EPF-suspected colonies was consistent; therefore, a single representative isolate per site was selected for molecular identification. This approach ensured efficient confirmation of EPF identity while avoiding redundancy, as morphologically similar colonies from the same site were assumed to belong to the same genus.

DNA extraction

DNA extraction of each selected isolate was carried out via the technique of (Punia et al. (2019) with minor adjustments. Fungal masses of each suspected EPF isolate were harvested from potato dextrose broth (PDB). The harvested fungal masses were then macerated individually with CTAB lysis buffer (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA) containing 100 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8), 20 mM EDTA, 1.4 M NaCl, and 2% CTAB. In addition, 2 μl of β -mercaptoethanol (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA) and 10 μl of 10% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA) were added. Afterwards, 30 μl of proteinase K (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA) was added, and the mixture was incubated overnight at 56°C in a water bath. After this, DNA was extracted with a chloroform: isoamyl alcohol mixture (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA) (24:1, v/v). Finally, ethanol (Honeywell, USA) washing was performed to precipitate the DNA. After two washes, each DNA sample was rehydrated with low-TE buffer (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA). A Thermo Scientific NanoDrop 1000 spectrophotometer was used to measure the quantity of extracted gDNA at 260 nm.

Amplification of the ITS gene sequences through PCR and DNA sequencing

The ITS region of the selected fungal isolates was amplified using the primers ITS1 and ITS2 (Table 2) in 25 µL PCRs. Each reaction contained 12.5 µl of 2× PCR master mix (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA), 3 µl of genomic DNA template, 0.5 µl of each primer, and 8.5 µl of nuclease-free water (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA). PCR amplification was performed in a Bio-Rad thermocycler under the following conditions: initial denaturation at 95°C for 3 min, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 s, annealing at 55°C for 1 min, and extension at 72°C for 2 min, with a final extension at 72°C for 10 min.

Table 1. Sequences of Primers used in the ITS analysis.

Primer Name	Sequences 5' -3'	References
ITS1	5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3'	(Gardes and Bruns 1993; White 1990)
ITS2	5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3'	

The amplified products were separated on a 1.5% agarose gel at 110 V for 35 minutes to confirm the presence of the expected ITS band. PCR products were purified and subjected to bidirectional Sanger sequencing. Chromatograms were edited in BioEdit v7.2.5 by trimming low-quality bases to obtain high-confidence sequences.

Species level identification was conducted with BLASTn by comparing sequences against the NCBI GenBank database. The sequences were deposited in the GenBank-NCBI database with accession numbers PQ285129, PQ551091, and PQ415785. Representative fungal species sequences from GenBank (Table 3) were used for the comparative molecular analysis. Multiple sequence alignments were achieved through ClustalW in MEGA v11 with default gap opening (15) and extension (6.66) penalties. Phylogenetic reconstruction was achieved with the neighbour-joining method with 1000 bootstrap replications, the Tamura-Nei model being used to calculate evolutionary distances. The ITS sequence of *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 16883 (GenBank ID NR_111041) served as the outgroup.

Table 2. Retrieved ITS sequences from GenBank that were used as references.

Species	ID number	References
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	MT239408	(Medo et al. 2021)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	MT239418	(Medo et al. 2021)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	MF872379	(Lestari 2016)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	MT239489	(Medo et al. 2021)

<i>B. bassiana</i>	MT239415	(Medo et al. 2021)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	MT239417	(Medo et al. 2021)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	MT239410	(Medo et al. 2021)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	NR 111594	GenBank
<i>Trichoderma longibrachiatum</i>	OP710045	(Bakhshi et al. 2023)
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	OM060242	GenBank
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	MW485611	GenBank
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	MK391142	GenBank
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	OL953191	GenBank
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	NR 120298	GenBank
<i>Purpureocillium lilacinum</i>	ON853881	(Monpierre et al. 2022)
<i>P. lilacinum</i>	KJ415582	GenBank
<i>P. lilacinum</i>	KJ415586	GenBank
<i>P. lilacinum</i>	KJ415585	GenBank
<i>P. lilacinum</i>	KJ415579	GenBank
<i>P. lilacinum</i>	NR 165946	GenBank

Results

Morphological and microscopic identification of EPF

Numerous fungal genera were observed in soil samples collected from fertile agricultural fields, fruit orchards, vegetation-rich areas, and semi-hilly zones across Punjab, Balochistan, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan (Table 4). Morphological characterization of the isolates was based on colony features and spore structures, which led to the identification of several entomopathogenic fungal (EPF) genera, including *Beauveria*, *Trichoderma*, and *Purpureocillium*. Other predominant genera recorded included *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria*, and *Cladosporium*. The primary objective of this study was the isolation and identification of EPF using culture-based techniques, and the diversity of fungal isolates obtained reflects the ecological variability and rich microbial biodiversity of the sampled regions.

Morphological examination of the fungal colonies revealed distinct patterns across the sampled sites. In Killa Saif Ullah–Muslim Baagh (MB), all ten samples yielded colonies corresponding to the genus *Beauveria*. In contrast, samples from the Islamabad–Lahore Motorway, near the capital territory of Islamabad (IM), and Sharan Forest (S) contained colonies identified as *Trichoderma* and *Purpureocillium*, respectively. Although these EPF were the focus of the study, other saprophytic fungi; including *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria*, and *Cladosporium* were also recorded. However, these genera did not exhibit the defining morphological characteristics of EPF, such as distinctive colony pigmentation, powdery or velvety conidial

surfaces, erect conidiophores, and chains or clusters of conidia, and were therefore not processed further.

For the morphological identification of these three EPFs, colony characteristics and conidial morphology were observed. *B. bassiana* (MB) colonies isolated from Muslim Bagh, Balochistan were fluffy, wooly, and powdery in appearance with irregular edges and was white to cream in colour (Figure 2a). The conidiophores were in zig-zag ramifications (Figure 2b), which is the core characteristic of the genus *Beauveria*. The conidia were single or grouped, and their size ranged from 2–3 μm ; the conidia were hyaline, single-cell shaped, and circular to oval shaped (Figure 2c). In contrast, *T. longibrachiatum* (IM) colonies from Islamabad–Lahore Motorway, near the capital territory, Islamabad, ranged from white to dark greenish gray (Figure 3a). The texture was velvety, and the growth was concentric with irregular or undulating edges. The conidia were circular or ellipsoidal, green, and smooth, and their size varied from 3–5 μm . Additionally, branching and septate hyphae were observed (Figure 3b). Finally, *P. lilacinum* (S) colonies from Sharan initially appeared white and later turned lilac in appearance (Figure 4a); it was bulged and round in shape. The conidia were single-cell shaped, chain-like, and slightly oval to elongated in shape, and were 2–3 μm in size. The hyphae were septate (Figure 4b). Its lilac or purple colour is the core characteristic of this fungus. To understand the morphological and microscopic characteristics more acutely, Table 5) can be referred to.

Table 4. Summary of Soil Samples, EPF Occurrence, and Sample Codes

S.No	Province	Site Name	Sample Codes	Total Samples	EPF Observed	Notes on Other Fungi
1	Balochistan	Killa Saif Ullah–Muslim Baagh	MB-1 to MB-10	10	Yes – <i>Beauveria</i>	Other saprophytic fungi present
2	Balochistan	Loralai	LO-1 to LO-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
3	Balochistan	Chaman	CH-1 to CH-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
4	Balochistan	Kalat	KL-1 to KL-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
5	Balochistan	Sibi	SB-1 to SB-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
6	Balochistan	Zhob	ZH-1 to ZH-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
7	Balochistan	Quetta	QU-1 to QU-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
8	Punjab	Islamabad–Lahore Motorway	IM-1 to IM-10	10	Yes – <i>Trichoderma</i>	Other saprophytic fungi present
9	Punjab	Lahore	LA-1 to LA-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
10	Punjab	Jhelum	JH-1 to JH-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
11	Punjab	Rawalpindi	RA-1 to RA-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed

12	Punjab	Multan	MU-1 to MU-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
13	Punjab	Faisalabad	FA-1 to FA-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
14	Punjab	Jhang	JG-1 to JG-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
15	Punjab	Nankana Sahib	NS-1 to NS-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
16	Punjab	Bahawalpur	BH-1 to BH-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
17	Punjab	Dera Ghazi Khan	DG-1 to DG-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
18	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Sharan Forest	S-1 to S-10	10	Yes – <i>Purpureocillium</i>	Other saprophytic fungi present
19	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Shamozai	SM-1 to SM-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
20	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Swat	SW-1 to SW-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
21	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Usho Forest	UF-1 to UF-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
22	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Kashora	KA-1 to KA-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
23	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Sheringal	SH-1 to SH-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
24	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Abbottabad	AB-1 to AB-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
25	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Haripur	HA-1 to HA-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
26	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Malam Jabba	MJ-1 to MJ-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
27	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	Kumrat	KU-1 to KU-10	10	No	Only saprophytic fungi observed
Total	–	–	–	270	30	Other saprophytic fungi recorded in all samples

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2: (a). White to cream, fluffy, woolly and powdery mildew colonies of the MB-2 isolate. (b) and (c). Microscopic zig-zag ramification of conidiophores was observed via lactophenol cotton blue staining. (c) Circular to oval-shaped spores.

Figure 3. (a) Dark greenish gray colony of IM-10. (b) Green- or ellipsoidal-shaped conidia with branched septate hyphae.

Figure 4. (a) Lilac-coloured colony of the S-1 isolate. (b) Lactophenol cotton blue stain enhanced the contrast and made hyphae, phialides, and conidia easily visible.

Table 5. Morphological and microscopic characteristics of the isolated EPFs

Isolated fungi code	Surface Colony Morphology			Conidia size	Conidia shape
	Colony colour	Appearance of colony	Edges	Microscopic examination	
MB-2	White to cream	Fluffy, woolly, and powdery	Irregular edges	2-3 μm	Hyaline, single-cell and circular to oval shaped
IM-10	White to dark greenish grey	Velvety with concentric growth	Irregular or undulate edges	3-5 μm	Green coloured circular or ellipsoidal shaped

S-1	Lilac	Powdery and velvety	Bulged and raised	2-3 μm	Small, chain like, slightly oval to elongated shape
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Molecular identification of EPF

The molecular diagnosis of the isolated fungi revealed the presence of three EPFs, *B. bassiana*, *T. longibrachiatum*, and *P. lilacinum*. PCR amplification of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of rRNA generated fragments of approximately 600 bp for all isolates (Figure 5).

Phylogenetic analysis of the ITS sequences using the neighbor-joining method with 1000 bootstrap replications revealed that the three isolates clustered with their corresponding reference species. Selected fungus isolated from Killa Saif Ullah samples clustered with multiple *Beauveria bassiana* reference sequences with 100% bootstrap support, confirming its identity as *B. bassiana*. On the other hand, fungus isolated from Sharan samples grouped with *Purpureocillium lilacinum* reference sequences, also with 100% bootstrap support, validating its species identity. Similarly, fungus isolated from Islamabad–Lahore Motorway, near the capital territory of Islamabad clustered with *Trichoderma longibrachiatum* reference sequences with 100% bootstrap support, confirming its identification. No significant intraspecific variation was observed within each clade, indicating high genetic similarity between the isolates and their respective reference sequences. *A. flavus* was used as an outgroup, confirming the evolutionary divergence of the EPF isolates (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Fragment sizes of the PCR-amplified ITS regions of all the isolates obtained via gel electrophoresis. On the left side, bands of the DNA ladder scale (M) are shown.

Figure 6. A phylogenetic tree was constructed via the neighbor-joining method, showing the relationships among fungal isolates of *B. bassiana*, *P. lilacinum*, and *T. longibrachiatum*. Strong support can be observed at key nodes (100%), and bootstrap values (in percentages) reflect the accuracy of clustering. Newly characterized isolates are indicated with yellow dots, and *A. flavus* serves as an outgroup.

Discussion

Understanding the presence of insect pathogens and using them as part of an integrated pest management plan is the first step in creating a microbial control program (Gandarilla-Pacheco et al. 2021). The widespread and frequent use of extremely hazardous and persistent synthetic insecticides has resulted in modern problems with environmental contamination and health risks. As a result, it is necessary to search for safer and more environmentally friendly pest control alternatives, such as EPF, which has proven effective against a variety of insect pest species (Ullah et al. 2022).

The present study isolated and identified indigenous entomopathogenic fungi (EPFs) from ecologically diverse regions of Pakistan using a combination of morphological, microscopic, and ITS-based molecular approaches. While the current research focused on isolating entomopathogenic fungi, the soil samples were mainly dominated by rapidly growing saprophytic genera like *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria*, and *Cladosporium*. This aligns with both national and international studies that identify these genera as prevalent soil residents due to their quick sporulation, adaptable nutrient use, and robust resistance to environmental changes (Gopane et al. 2021; Niaz et al. 2024).

The fungal communities clearly mirrored ecological differences across provinces. In Balochistan's semi-arid soils, fungi adapted to low moisture conditions were prevalent. In contrast, Punjab's irrigated and heavily farmed soils were rich in fast-growing saprophytes (Nisar et al. 2025). The forested soils of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa harbored a more varied community, with a higher presence of fungi linked to organic-rich environments. These findings support established principles that factors like soil moisture, organic content, pH, vegetation cover, and land use influence fungal composition (Qayyum et al. 2021a). Given that Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa have been less studied in the past, this research provides valuable insights into the diversity of entomopathogenic fungi in these areas.

These findings demonstrate that Pakistan's contrasting agro-ecological zones act as distinct ecological filters that shape fungal community composition and the natural occurrence of entomopathogenic fungi. The recovery of EPFs from arid, irrigated, and forested systems highlights their ecological adaptability and suggests that native strains may be better suited for local pest management than introduced commercial isolates. Such zone-specific occurrence emphasizes the importance of ecological context when selecting EPFs for sustainable biological control programs.

The distribution of EPFs in this study was influenced by the geography of the sampling sites. The present study highlights the discovery of *B. bassiana* in Killa Saif Ullah-Muslim Baagh (wheat crops), Balochistan. This finding presents an intriguing opportunity to investigate the ecological preferences and geographic range of this species. *B. bassiana* is the most prevalent fungus in the soil of agricultural fields (Meyling and Eilenberg 2006). According to a study by (Hussein et al. 2010), *B. bassiana* was more prevalent in wheat fields. Similarly, in the present study, *B. bassiana* appeared to be more dominant within the wheat crop area (Sun et al. 2008) also detected *B.*

bassiana from crop fields. In Pakistan, the harvesting of wheat starts from March to May; thus, to ensure that this occurs, the sample was collected in May. The optimum temperature for wheat crop growth is 25°C, which supports the growth of these entomopathogens (Faryal and Ayaz 2015). The fact that it exists in Balochistan correlates with claims that *B. bassiana* is a cosmopolitan species that grows in temperate, humid, and subtropical climates. It is frequently found in agricultural settings, where it can be used to manage pest populations biologically. Similar associations of *B. bassiana* with wheat and cereal-based agroecosystems have been reported from neighboring countries, including China and Iran (Liu et al. 2025; Torkaman et al. 2023), indicating that such cropping systems provide favorable microhabitats for this cosmopolitan species. This regional consistency supports the ecological role of *B. bassiana* as a naturally occurring regulator of insect pests in cereal-growing environments.

In the present study, *T. longibrachiatum* was isolated from a vegetative area of Punjab, Pakistan. A study by (NV 2022) revealed that this fungus has also been identified in healthy vegetable crops, indicating that it may be employed as a biocontrol agent to prevent soil-borne diseases. Furthermore, it has been shown to have entomopathogenic properties, particularly for pests (Anwar et al. 2016). Research from different regions has shown that *T. longibrachiatum* can be found in a variety of environments, such as agricultural soils and industrial wastewater. This versatility emphasizes the importance of local environmental factors, such as soil texture and moisture content, contributing to the development and potency of this fungus as a biocontrol agent (Bint-e-Zahira et al. 2024). This reveals how *T. longibrachiatum* may be able to adapt to a range of ecological niches, including those connected to the agricultural practices of Punjab. Comparable isolates of *T. longibrachiatum* have been documented from agricultural soils in India (Ghosh and Pal 2016), where they exhibit both entomopathogenic activity and antagonism against soil-borne plant pathogens. This dual functional role enhances its ecological and applied significance in intensively cultivated systems such as those prevalent in Punjab.

The discovery of *P. lilacinum* in the forest regions of KPK, Pakistan, marked a breakthrough in our knowledge of this organism and its ability to be used for biological control. A study by (Jamil et al. 2020) demonstrated that *P. lilacinum* was isolated from forests in northern Pakistan. Thus, the presence of this fungus in the forest area of Abbottabad, Pakistan, aligns with the findings of our study. It has remarkable biocontrol properties. Studies have shown how well it suppresses populations of root-knot nematodes such as *Meloidogyne incognita*, which are known to cause

large losses in agriculture (Khan and Tanaka 2023). Furthermore, *P. lilacinum* grows well in KPK because of its favourable climate. The fungus can flourish at different temperatures (8–38°C) and pH values; however, 26–30°C is usually the ideal range for its growth. The present study represents the first report of *P. lilacinum* from Sharan Forest, Pakistan, extending its known ecological distribution and highlighting the biocontrol potential of native forest soils in the region.

In the present study, molecular identification was selectively performed only on isolates that exhibited distinct morphological features characteristic of entomopathogenic fungi. This targeted strategy ensured that resources were directed toward isolates with genuine biocontrol potential rather than sequencing the dominant saprophytic flora. Unlike previous studies in Pakistan (Hameed et al. 2016; Iqbal et al. 2025; Qayyum et al. 2021b; Riaz et al. 2024; Wakil et al. 2013; Wakil et al. 2014), which relied solely on morphological identification, molecular confirmation in this study eliminates misidentification risks and allows precise species-level resolution. Furthermore, several local studies investigating EPF pathogenicity have used commercial or previously established strains of *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, and *Verticillium lecanii* rather than newly isolated indigenous strains (Iqbal et al. 2021; Raza et al. 2025), which limits ecological relevance and overlooks the potential of native diversity. In contrast, the present study integrates morphological screening with ITS-based molecular confirmation of newly recovered, indigenous isolates, thereby ensuring accurate species-level identification and providing a stronger, more reliable foundation for subsequent bioassay, formulation, and field-level development.

The low natural recovery of EPFs relative to saprophytic fungi in the present study aligns with recent evidence that entomopathogens face substantial ecological limitations in open soil environments. Several contemporary studies (Khan et al. 2025; Qayyum et al. 2021a; Rajput et al. 2024) highlight that EPFs are highly sensitive to abiotic stress, which restricts their persistence and natural abundance. UV-B radiation has been shown to markedly reduce spore germination and viability, thereby limiting the survival of exposed conidia in surface soils (Sutanto et al. 2022). In addition to environmental pressures, strain-level genetic variability determines whether isolates possess thermotolerance, desiccation resistance, or the ability to survive in nutrient-poor soils, and only a small proportion of naturally occurring EPFs appear to carry such adaptive traits (DanChao et al. 2025; Ni et al. 2025). Collectively, these ecological constraints provide a strong explanation for the recovery of only three EPF isolates despite extensive sampling across diverse regions.

Rather than indicating methodological limitations, this pattern reflects a genuine ecological bottleneck that shapes the distribution and detectability of EPFs in harsh or disturbed soil systems. Modern formulation strategies, including oil-based formulations and microencapsulation, have been widely demonstrated to enhance the environmental persistence of EPFs (Baldiviezo et al. 2023; Behle et al. 2009; de Jesus Seabra et al. 2024; De Oliveira et al. 2018; Meirelles et al. 2023; Mohamed et al. 2024). These advances demonstrate that appropriate formulation can convert sensitive EPF isolates into more persistent and field-ready biocontrol agents. Alongside formulation improvements, integrating molecular screening and genomic characterisation is crucial for selecting isolates with innate thermotolerance, desiccation resistance, and high virulence, supporting the development of next-generation, locally adapted EPF products.

Conclusion

This study provides new insights into the limited yet ecologically significant diversity of indigenous entomopathogenic fungi in Balochistan, Punjab and KPK. Despite harsh environmental conditions, these provinces harbour native EPF isolates with promising biocontrol potential. The selective molecular confirmation of suspected EPFs, combined with detailed profiling of soil fungal communities, establishes a reliable framework for future exploration and application. Given the environmental pressures that constrain EPF persistence, including UV exposure, temperature extremes, and soil desiccation, it is essential to expand strain isolation efforts and prioritise molecular characterisation to accurately identify and select robust, locally adapted isolates. Complementary advances in formulation science, such as oil-based and microencapsulation technologies can further enhance conidial survival, thermal tolerance, and field efficacy. By integrating ecological understanding, molecular tools, and modern formulation approaches, this research lays the groundwork for developing next-generation, region-specific EPF-based biopesticides, supporting sustainable and biologically driven pest management strategies tailored to Pakistan's diverse agroecological landscapes.

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